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Sociological approaches to the phenomenon of self-presentation

Annotation. It is worth saying that nowadays the study of various communicative practices of everyday life deserves special attention from researchers. Within the framework of this article, we attempt a comprehensive review of various theories and concepts of self-presentation, considered mainly from a sociological perspective. Self-presentation is considered as an integral part of everyday communicative practice; the main aspects of this phenomenon are studied and analyzed from the point of views of various researchers. In the article self-presentation is considered mainly as of self-Image formation (G. Mead, Ch. Cooley), as one of the main aspects of social anxiety (B. Schlenker and M. Weigold, M. Leary and R. Kowalski), as motivation to achieve or avoid failures (R. Arkin, A. Schutz), as the desire for power (I. Jones, T. Pittman). Such aspect of self-presentation as awareness of the process (R. Baumeister and A. Steinhilber, J. Tedeshi and M. Riess) are also considered. Special attention is payed to the key social drama concept of E. Goffman, described in his work "Presentation of Self in Everyday Life".

Key words: everyday life, social practices, communicative practices, self-presentation.

The reality of the modern world makes necessary the comprehensive and detailed study of everyday life with all of the variety of its different social practices that make up its culture. In the context of the information society development, there are not only qualitatively new types of social practices formation, but also the former practices continue to preserve and update. This ensures the coherence and continuity of the everyday life culture reproduction as a whole, and this allows it to be one of the basic, fundamental components of social life. The study of everyday life allows us to create a multidimensional picture of culture and society in their inconsistency and integrity. This role puts the study of everyday life at the center of modern social research [17]. It should be noted that social processes, including the social existence of each individual, are now increasingly defined in terms and concepts of the theory and practice of communication. The rapid development of post-industrial society with its defining value of knowledge, the continuous flow of information and the development of new social communication channels, media, the Internet – these realities are firmly established not only in science but also in everyday life. The study of communicative practices is the basis for the formulation of broad philosophical generalizations and terms. In turn, this can help to make a rational explanation of the different social phenomenon [5, p. 1]. In this article we try to make a socio-psychological analysis of one of the main aspects of everyday communicative practice – self-presentation. Self-presentation is the integral part of everyday communication, and often unconsciously included in the process of interpersonal interaction. Therefore this requires a special attention from the sociological point of view.

From the very start it is necessary to point out that nowadays in science there are a large number of scientific theories that explain and describe the phenomenon of self-presentation in terms of different approaches. We can talk about each theory in detail, but the purpose of this article is to consider this concept within the framework of sociology and social psychology, because the phe-

phenomenon of self-presentation is a complex and multifaceted socio-psychological phenomenon that requires a comprehensive study.

It may be as well to say, at the outset, that despite the fact that the interest in self-presentation has existed in science for a long time, there is still no generalized understanding of this phenomenon. This also can be explained by the uncertainty of the scope and content of the concept. The term self-presentation is generally used as a synonym for impression management, to refer to the many strategies and techniques used in the creation and control of the external image and self-image which demonstrates to others.

We shall now proceed to show the main theoretical and methodological approaches to the phenomenon of self-presentation in modern sociology. Each theory focuses on different aspects of this phenomenon, so for the most complete analysis of self-presentation phenomenon, we will try to make a comprehensive study.

In the tradition of interactionism, self-presentation is seen as a means of self-image formation and self-concept. Herbert Mead and Charles Cooley supported the idea that in social discourse and interaction it is typical for a person to show different social faces to different partners in order to present himself in the most beneficial way and make the best impression, and then form his own idea of himself, reflecting the opinions and behavior of others. From this it follows that according to G. Mead and Ch. Cooley, the knowledge of the individual about himself is a reflection of the knowledge of others about him [11, pp. 146-155; 4, pp. 66-103].

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that, in general, in the interactionist concept, the term «I» means primarily individual's own actions at the social arena. Thus, knowledge about himself is a consequence of what is happening in the social arena. And the individual, in turn, needs to express what he has inside to the others. "The Looking Glass self" (Ch. Cooley) and "Self" (G. Mead) are based on the opinions and attitudes, received from the outside world. Both concepts are similar, with the only difference that, according to G. Mead, the idea of "I" contains only a cognitive component, in other words, the individual's knowledge about himself.

Similar views on self-presentation have B. Schlenker and M. Weigold [15], as well as M. Leary and R. Kowalski [9], who believe that this is characteristic for the individual, intentionally or unintentionally, to seek to present the desired self-image in the eyes of others and in their own eyes. They consider self-presentation mainly in the context of social anxiety. Social anxiety arises when people are motivated to make a preferred impression on real or imagined audiences but doubt they will do so, and thus perceive or imagine unsatisfactory evaluative reactions from subjectively important audiences. They presume that specific situational and dispositional antecedents of social anxiety operate by influencing people's motivation to impress others and their expectations of satisfactorily doing so [10, 16]. The opposite feeling is characterized by the expectation of satisfaction, which forms a sense of security, confidence in the future, calmness and optimism [2].

D. Myers considers self-presentation as a means of maintaining high self-esteem. The main idea of his theory, described in "Social psychology", is that most people have an inflated self-esteem, based on an optimistic attitude towards themselves. This self-esteem requires constant support from others and is manifested through the desire to please and make a special impression, expressed in a special behavior [13, pp. 68-72].

The next point concerns self-presentation as a behavioral realization of motivation. R. Arkin and A. Schutz see in self-presentation the realization of motivation to achieve or avoid failures and distinguish on this basis two types of self-presentation: acquiring self-presentation (motivation to achieve), protective self-presentation (motivation to avoid failures) [1, 19].

Acquiring self-presentation represents the motivation of achievement. First of all, it is characterized by the choice of tasks and roles corresponding to the social status, level of education, financial status and other similar aspects of social life. The choice of the interaction environment corresponding to the level of identification of the individual also includes. In other words, the person communicates with an «equal» to himself.

Protective self-presentation is a behavioral expression of the motivation to avoid failure. This type of self-presentation is unconsciously revealed in individual's behavior when he chooses an inappropriate social environment for solving his problems, either with too low requirements or with too high. A self-presentation in terms of excessive demands so-called adventuristic.

R. Baumeister and A. Steinhilber argue in the line of awareness-unawareness of the self-presentation process. They define self-presentation as a process that is completely unconscious, which reflects individual's social nature and the need of recognition by others. According to this concept, self-presentation is a process of self-disclosure in interpersonal communication and interaction through the demonstration of individual's own thoughts, character, etc [3].

The opposite point of view at the process of self-presentation is held by J. Tedeshi and M. Riess. According to them, self-presentation is absolutely conscious individual's behavior aimed at creating a certain impression [20].

Now we shall turn our attention to another theory. I. Jones and T. Pittman believe that the basis of self-presentation is the desire to expand and maintain influence in interpersonal relations, in other words, the desire for power. On this basis, they determine five strategies of self-presentation, each of them is aimed at obtaining a certain kind of power.

1. Ingratiation. This strategy obliges others to be kind and friendly to the subject. This way the power of charm achieves.

2. Self promotion. This strategy provides an opportunity to promote the competence and also gives the power of an expert.

3. Intimidation. Demonstration of force obliges others to obey. This way the power of fear achieves.

4. Exemplification. Demonstration of spiritual superiority. This way the power of a mentor achieves.

5. Supplication. Demonstration of weakness that gives the power of compassion.

According to I. Jones and T. Pittman, strategies impose on others a certain way of behavior to the subject [8].

As we have mentioned, there is in modern sociology, there are also a large number of approaches to the phenomenon of self-presentation. Most of them cannot be told here in details. Now let us look more specifically at one of the main theories of self-presentation in sociology.

The most significant contribution to the study of self-presentation mechanisms was made by the famous sociologist Erving Goffman. He created the concept of social drama, in which he considered the process of self-presentation through the performance of social roles. His well-known work «Presentation of Self in Everyday Life» became for many years a paradigm basis for the analysis of self-presentation phenomenon. We must now briefly look at common characteristics of this theory.

The work is devoted to social interaction and management of the impression about this interaction. The everyday life world according to E. Goffman is an order of direct people's interactions, which is based on stable forms of experience interpretation – frames [6]. He pays special attention to the structure of social contacts, direct interactions of people. By interpreting them, E. Goffman draws an analogy with the theater, in this connection, his theory is traditionally defined as the concept of social drama. In his work «Presentation of Self in Everyday Life» E. Goffman studies the main means, methods and actions by which an individual, as a skilled actor, creates the desired version of himself [7]. E. Goffman states that when a person appears in front of others, others usually seek to gather information about him or build their behavior based on information that they already own. They will be interested in his socio-economic status, attitude towards them, competence etc. Information about a person helps to determine the nature of the situation, allow understanding what a person expects from others and what they can expect from him. Realizing this, others will know how best to behave in order to further cause the desired reaction.

They can also rely on the assumption of some psychological traits as a means of predicting the present and future individual's behavior. An individual should behave in a specific way for, in-

tentionally or unintentionally, express himself. So others will, in turn, be impressed by him in some way. An audience, according to E. Goffman, can only make different assumptions, according to individual's behavior.

Let's move from the position of the audience to the individual's point of view, who presents himself in front of them. A person, in turn, may want others to have a high opinion of him or think that he has a high opinion of them. He can give a sense of what he feels is actually or produce a confused impression. In his interest it may be to control their behavior, especially their attitude towards him. Thus, when an individual appears in front of the audience, he has to mobilize his activity to convey the impression in which he is interested.

Thus, according to E. Goffman, when a person appears in front of other people in whom he is interested (the audience), he must mobilize his activity to make the right impression. This aimed for:

- 1). To cause the desired reaction;
- 2). To appear with «the right face»;
- 3). Because an audience expects such behavior from a representative of this group;
- 4). Because a social role requires this;
- 5). Otherwise, an individual risks being misunderstood, and this can change the whole situation;

- 6). To come to "understanding" and thus he achieves his goals.

An important aspect of self-presentation, according To E. Goffman, is dramatization. When a person appears in front of others, he usually includes in his acting some components designed to shed light and make clear some facts about him and the whole situation. He must mobilize his activity in such way to express what he wants to convey to the audience in the process of self-presentation.

Another important aspect of socialization is idealization. In front of other people, an individual should be a model of accepted behavior in this society, even more - his whole life should be like that. The world is one big ceremony.

However, according to E. Goffman, idealization should not be perceived in the negative way. It can be perceived as a way to achieve the ideal by the creation of a more perfect reality than the one that exists at the moment. It should be noted that a person is forced to create such impression, because this is the only possible behavior prescribed by the rules.

It should be added in this connection, that in his work, E. Goffman dwells on many aspects of self-presentation, and we should note that this work is a kind of starting point in the study of self-presentation, it inspired a number of empirical studies, which, in turn, confirmed or refuted the assumptions of E. Goffman.

In Russian science, the phenomenon of self-presentation was most often considered from a psychological point of view, but, nevertheless, we can name some modern researchers who consider this phenomenon from the perspective of social psychology, based on the theories described above: Shkuratova I. P. [18], Mikhailova E. M. [12], Pikuleva O. A. [14] etc.

Summarizing the above, it should be note that most researchers of self-presentation phenomenon consider it in the context of social interaction in everyday life. It should be said that self-presentation is a general, fundamental characteristic of social behavior, which takes both conscious and unconscious character. It is the condition for the appropriate perception of the individual by others, the only possible way to achieve mutual understanding within the framework of the specific social situation in society. It is a complex integrated system of interrelated components, which is determined by the presence of the subject-object activity in varying degrees of awareness, the characteristics of the situation and the object of self-presentation, personal characteristics of self-presentation subject. Self-presentation is an integral socio-psychological phenomenon manifested in human behavior in situations of social interaction, due to personal, motivational and situational factors, that requires close attention from researchers for the most holistic understanding of the social interaction nature in particular and the course of all social processes in the culture of everyday life

as a whole. In this article we have been able to present only small amount of different self-presentation theories and nowadays this problem still requires detailed study from different points of view.

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